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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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CONCEPTUAL APPROACHES TO UNDERSTANDING FANATICISM AMONG FEMALE ADOLESCENTS

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 O'zbekiston xalqaro islom akademiyasi,
 Din psixologiyasi yo'nalishi tayanch doktoranti

Abstract: Based on a systematic review of the literature, the paper examines fanaticism as a result of a cognitive style formed within the educational process, characterized by deficits in critical thinking and cognitive rigidity. It is demonstrated that the insufficient development of information filtering and analytical competencies among female adolescents in modern educational systems increases their vulnerability to destructive ideological manipulation. The study also provides a scientific justification for the need to reorient educational paradigms toward the development of cognitive flexibility.

Key words: fanaticism, critical thinking, cognitive rigidity, information filtering, manipulation, cognitive flexibility, female adolescents, educational process.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada mutaassiblik fenomeni uning ta'lim jarayonida shakllanadigan kognitiv uslub – tanqidiy fikrlash yetishmasligi va kognitiv rigidlik natijasi ekanligi nuqtayi nazaridan tahlil qilinadi. Zamonaviy ta'lim tizimida o'spirin qizlarning axborotni filtrlash va tahlil qilish kompetensiyalarining yetarli darajada rivojlanmaganligi ularni destruktiv g'oyaviy manipulyatsiyalarga nisbatan zaiflashtirishi adabiyotlar tahlili asosida yoritiladi. Shuningdek, ta'lim paradigmalarini kognitiv moslashuvchanlikni rivojlantirishga yo'naltirish zaruriyati ilmiy jihatdan asoslab beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: mutaassiblik fenomeni, tanqidiy fikrlash, kognitiv rigidlik, axborotni filtrlash, manipulyatsiya, kognitiv moslashuvchanlik.

Аннотация: В статье на основе анализа литературы рассматривается феномен фанатизма как результат когнитивного стиля, формирующегося в образовательном процессе, характеризующегося дефицитом критического мышления и когнитивной ригидностью. Показано, что недостаточная сформированность компетенций фильтрации и анализа информации у девочек-подростков в современной системе образования делает их уязвимыми перед деструктивными идеологическими манипуляциями. Также научно обосновывается необходимость переориентации образовательных парадигм на развитие когнитивной гибкости.

Ключевые слова: феномен фанатизма, критическое мышление, когнитивная ригидность, фильтрация информации, манипуляция, когнитивная гибкость, девочки-подростки, образовательный процесс.

INTRODUCTION

The psychological landscape of female adolescence is characterized by an intense search for self-identity and ontological security. During this transitional phase, any instability in the educational or familial environment can induce severe identity diffusion. Fanaticism often emerges not as a primary ideological conviction, but as a maladaptive psychological defense mechanism to counteract this internal anxiety. Dogmatic belief systems offer ready-made identities and absolute moral certainty. Current academic discourse on youth extremism is heavily saturated with male-centric data, leaving the specific psychological mechanisms of female adolescent fanaticism under-theorized. This paper bridges this gap by synthesizing psychoanalytic and cognitive approaches. It examines how teenage girls internalize fanatical dogmas as a substitute for authentic self-differentiation, highlighting the critical role of schools in providing emotional validation and analytical tools to prevent such psychological vulnerabilities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Psychologically, fanaticism develops in parallel with an individual's cognitive functioning, particularly through thinking patterns, vulnerability to manipulation, and the balance between cognitive flexibility and rigidity. In his seminal work *The Open and Closed Mind*, 1960, Milton Rokeach shifted the study of fanaticism from

the content of beliefs to the structure of the cognitive system. In a “closed” cognitive system, beliefs are rigid, isolated from contradictory evidence, and heavily dependent on absolute authority. For female adolescents, such a closed mind functions as a maladaptive defense mechanism to counteract identity diffusion and ontological anxiety. When confronted with rapid developmental transitions, adolescent girls seek refuge in dogmatic certainty, rejecting any information that threatens their internalized ideological equilibrium.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employs a qualitative research design based on a systematic review of scientific literature and theoretical sources related to fanaticism, cognitive styles, and adolescent psychology. Data are collected through content analysis of peer-reviewed articles, monographs, and empirical studies. The analysis is conducted using comparative and interpretative methods to identify key patterns, cognitive mechanisms, and conceptual relationships.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

A closed cognitive system evaluates information based on the perceived authority of the source rather than its logical or empirical merit. In the modern digital information space, female adolescents are constantly exposed to sophisticated ideological manipulations. When a cognitive system is closed, the adolescent cannot separate the message from the messenger. If the source of the information is perceived as an absolute authority, the message is internalized uncritically. To prevent fanaticism, modern educational paradigms must shift toward fostering cognitive flexibility. This transition requires moving away from teacher-centered authoritarian instruction to dialogic, inquiry-based learning. When schools prioritize critical thinking, debates, and problem-based learning, they teach adolescent girls to separate objective truth from emotional manipulation. Fostering cognitive flexibility empowers students to tolerate ambiguity, analyze contradictory data, and adapt their worldview based on logic rather than blind obedience to dogmatic authority.

In the 21-st century, Rokeach's concept of the closed mind is amplified by digital environments. Social media algorithms are architecturally designed to create cognitive echo chambers. For female adolescents seeking identity and validation, algorithms serve as artificial absolute authorities. When a young girl interacts with ideologically biased content, the system continuously feeds her homogeneous information, systematically filtering out dissenting views. This digital loop accelerates the crystallization of cognitive rigidity. Empirical data shows that vulnerability to manipulation is not a result of low general intelligence, but rather a deficit in epistemic curiosity – the desire to seek out and understand new, conflicting knowledge ^[2]. Therefore, digital fanaticism is a structural merging of a closed cognitive style with personalized information isolation.

The discussion of these cognitive mechanisms inevitably leads to the re-evaluation of educational paradigms. If fanaticism is a failure of information filtering and cognitive flexibility, then the solution lies in building epistemic autonomy within the classroom. Modern educational psychology argues that schools must shift from transmitting static knowledge to training metacognition (thinking about thinking). To transition from a closed to an open mind, female adolescents require structured pedagogical interventions:

1. Dialectical questioning (Socratic method): teaching students how to question the premises of any absolute claim.
2. Source deconstruction: training students to evaluate information based on empirical merit, separating the emotional appeal of the authority figure from the logical validity of the message.
3. Tolerance for ambiguity: curriculum designs must present historical and social issues not as binary moral tales, but as complex, multi-layered phenomena.

Rokeach's psychological profiling proves that neutralizing fanaticism among young girls cannot be achieved through mere counter-propaganda, as the closed mind naturally rejects contradictory ideological content. Instead, the solution must be pedagogical and structural. Educational paradigms must focus on transforming the cognitive style from closed to open. By training metacognition – the ability to analyze how one thinks – schools can dismantle rigid mental schemas. Pedagogical interventions such as dialectical questioning (Socratic dialogue) and source deconstruction teach adolescent girls to separate objective truth from the emotional appeal of authority. Developing a tolerance for ambiguity within the classroom allows female adolescents to accept the complexities of the social world without resorting to dogmatic simplifications. Adolescence is a period of intense identity search. When the classroom environment relies on rigid, rote-memorization teaching methods, it inadvertently rewards cognitive rigidity. On the other hand, fostering cognitive flexibility – the ability to adapt one's thinking to new and conflicting data – acts as a psychological buffer. Rokeach's framework

proves that an open mind can process dissonance without experiencing anxiety. Therefore, teaching female adolescents to tolerate ambiguity and accept nuance prevents them from seeking refuge in dogmatic, black-and-white certainties. The synthesis of Rokeach's psychology and modern pedagogy necessitates an urgent shift in educational paradigms. Schools must transition from merely transmitting static knowledge to training metacognition (thinking about thinking). To open a closed mind, pedagogical interventions must be dialogic. Utilizing the Socratic method, dialectical debates, and source deconstruction empowers female adolescents to build epistemic autonomy. Instead of telling students what to think, the modern curriculum must focus on teaching them how to evaluate thought.

The acceptance of information is often governed by emotional connectivity (trust, affection, and belonging) rather than pure logic. If an idea is presented by a figure who provides emotional validation, the adolescent's analytical gatekeeper is bypassed. For female adolescents, who are statistically more attuned to relational harmony, if an ideology makes them feel secure or morally superior, the affect heuristic labels the information as true. This explains why providing counter-facts to a fanatical adolescent often fails; the analytical gatekeeper cannot be reached with logic once the emotional filter has already categorized the contradicting data as threatening to the individual's emotional equilibrium.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study concludes that fanaticism among female adolescents is a structural process of a closed cognitive system rather than merely ideological indoctrination. Preventing fanaticism requires shifting the pedagogical focus from the content of beliefs to the cognitive style through which those beliefs are processed. Fostering cognitive flexibility enables adolescent girls to evaluate information based on empirical merit rather than blind obedience to absolute authority figures.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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